

Kinetic and Spectroscopic Studies of Substituted *N*-Benzylbenzohydroxamic Acids

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N-Substituted hydroxamic acids have acquired phenomenal importance because of their current uses¹. However, due to the hydrolysis of hydroxamic acids into the parent carboxylic acids and hydroxylamines in mineral acids severe problems are faced in achieving the desired objectives. Hence, the half-life periods for acidic hydrolysis of some substituted *N*-benzylbenzohydroxamic acid (BBHA) (**1a-g**) have been determined.

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|---------------------|-----------------------------------|----------------------------------|
| 1a: X = H | 1c: X = 4-Cl | 1e: X = 4-NO ₂ |
| 1b: X = 3-Cl | 1d: X = 4-F | 1f: X = 4-CH ₃ |
| | 1g: X = 4-OCH ₃ | |

Attempts have also been made to explain the structures of substituted derivatives on the basis of uv, ir and nmr spectral data. We reported earlier hydrolysis mechanism of unsubstituted and *N*-substituted hydroxamic acids². The kinetics and acidic hydrolysis of parent compound, i.e. BBHA has already been reported³. The present objective is also to study the effect of substituents and to test the validity of Hammett equation.

Results and Discussion

Strong ¹H nmr signals of compounds **1a-g** due to methyl and methylene protons are easily distinguished from one another because of differences in integrated intensity and splitting patterns⁴. The signals were obtained at δ 4.6–4.8 (2H, CH₂), 2.4 (3H, CH₃), 3.8 (3H, OCH₃) and 7.15–7.35 (ArH), the phenyl protons being essentially equivalent. Equivalent protons can not give rise to observable multiplicity even though they are strongly coupled⁵. The broadness of the peaks were also observed due to increase in the exchange rate of protons. The *J* values were found to be 6 Hz.

All the derivatives exhibited a strong ir band around 3 100 ± 50 (OH), and others at 1 620 ± 10 cm⁻¹(C=O), 1 320 ± 30 (C–N) and 920 ± 15 cm⁻¹ (N–O). The ν_{OH} and 540

ν_{C=O} modes appearing at lower frequencies are due to strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding⁶. This fact is also inferred from the studies of ir spectra of the above compounds at different dilutions in CHCl₃.

The electronic spectra of these derivatives in 95% ethanol showed λ_{max} in the range between 205–269 nm (ε_{max} 10 to 36 × 10³ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹), attributable to aromatic conjugation⁷. The absorption bands for the electron-attracting groups appear at longer wave lengths than that of the electron-repelling groups in the substituted hydroxamic acids.

Kinetic study : The results of the study (Table 2) are represented as

$$-\frac{d[\text{BBHA}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{BBHA}][\text{H}^+] \\ = k_{\psi}[\text{BBHA}]$$

The reaction is first order in catalytic acid (HCl) and also in the hydroxamic acid concentrations. The accepted mechanism for acid-catalysed hydrolysis of BBHA is represented³ as

The values of half-life periods are shown in Table 1. Hydroxamic acids with small half-life for hydrolytic reaction are discarded for analytical applications. The 4-Cl BBHA is most reactive, whereas 4-CH₃ BBHA is least reactive. It is observed that by changing the substituents in the *para*- and *meta*-positions, the order of rate constants follows the order : 4-CH₃ < 4-OCH₃ < 4-F < H < 3-Cl < 4-NO₂. The introduction of electron-attracting groups increases the rate of hydrolysis whereas electron-repelling one decreases the hydrolysis rate. The effect of substitution has been assessed by use of Hammett equation,

$$\log k/k_0 = \rho \sigma$$

TABLE I—OBSERVED FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND HALF-LIFE PERIODS OF SUBSTITUTED BBHA AT 55° IN 2.9 M HCl MEDIUM : 10% (V/V) DIOXANE

Compd. no.	σ^*	$k_p \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$T_{0.5}$ min
1a	0.00	17.5	66.0
b	0.37	18.8	61.4
c	0.23	19.1	60.5
d	0.06	16.6	69.6
e	0.78	19.9	58.0
f	-0.17	15.1	76.5
g	-0.27	17.7	65.3

*Ref. 10

The value of reaction constant $\rho = 0.241$ (correlation coefficient = 0.932 and standard deviation = 0.0189 for four substituents) is similar to that found for the hydrolysis of esters and amides⁸.

Experimental

All the hydroxamic acids were prepared by standard procedures⁹. All the compounds, except 1e (pale yellow), are white crystalline solids and are stable to normal storage : 1a, m.p. 108° (Found : C, 73.99; H, 5.76; N, 6.16. Calcd. for : C, 73.75; H, 5.68; N, 6.06%); b, 125–26°; c, 129–30°; e, 136°; f, 105°; g, 109°.

Electronic spectra (EtOH) were determined on a Specord Carl-Zeiss-Jena spectrophotometer, ir spectra (CHCl₃/nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃ + trifluoroacetic acid) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard.

The rates of hydrolysis were determined³ spectrophotometrically (Systronics 108) by following the decrease in the characteristic absorption of the hydroxamic acid-ferric chloride complex. Pseudo-first order rate constants were

obtained from the slope of the appropriate graph with numerical values computed by the method of least-squares. The half-life periods were calculated from first order rate constants. All the chemicals used are of A.R. grade.

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